

Supplementary Materials for

Obscure soil microbes and where to find them

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Appendix S1. Global maps cross-validation.

Using all data within the global database ($n = 235$), the percentages of predicted (maps) and observed phylotypes of unclassified bacteria and fungi were correlated. Results indicate that the predicted and observed values for the % of unclassified taxa within bacteria and fungi in the 235 locations studied were positively and significantly correlated for both bacteria ($r = 0.66$, $P < 0.001$; $n = 235$) and fungi ($r = 0.55$, $P < 0.001$; $n = 235$). I then repeated the global maps for unclassified bacteria and fungi using a 66.6% of random data within the original database ($n = 157$). I used the information from the remaining 33.3% of data ($n = 78$) to cross-validate these maps. Observed (78 independent samples) and predicted (maps) values for the % of phylotypes with an unknown phyla were positively and significantly correlated for both bacteria ($r = 0.55$, $P < 0.001$; $n = 78$) and fungi ($r = 0.65$, $P < 0.001$; $n = 78$). Moreover, global maps including all samples ($n = 235$) and those including 66% of the data ($n = 178$) were positively and significantly correlated for both bacteria ($r = 0.73$, $P < 0.001$; $n = 225530$) and fungi ($r = 0.91$, $P < 0.001$; $n = 225530$).

Figure S1. Locations included in this study (n = 235).

Unclassified bacteria

Unclassified fungi

Figure S2. Global atlas including the potential distribution of % of phylotypes of bacteria and fungi with an unknown phyla (unclassified bacteria and fungi) based on their natural co-occurrence with climatic (aridity index, maximum and minimum temperature, precipitation seasonality and mean diurnal temperature range), primary productivity, dominant ecosystem type (forest and grasslands), soil properties (total organic carbon, pH and texture) and UV light in 235 locations. See Fig. S1 for the locations of the 235 in this study. See Appendix S1 for a cross-validation of these maps.